

AN INVERSE PROBLEM IN DESIGNING LAMINATED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

An integrated approach is introduced for the solution of the inverse problem: which are the lamina orientation, laminate constitution, core quality and thickness combination ensuring specified objective(s) to be reached?

The solution is obtained by integrating around an associative data base - sensitivity analysis and mathematically stringent optimization methods (MMA-Method of Moving Asymptotes) with finite element analysis, interactive graphic pre- and post-processing and parametric modelling - as implemented in OASIS-ALADDIN.

This approach has been applied to the design of a composite blade with adaptive characteristics -i.e a blade with decreasing pitch for increasing loads.

Keywords: Inverse Problem, Optimization, Sensitivity Analysis, Composites, Adaptive Structures

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are today increasingly used for weight and/or performance sensitive structures. The heterogeneous nature of laminated fiber-reinforced composites allows engineers to customize the material and to design the structure as to reach an optimal solution, on a technical and economical basis. Given the number of parameters to take into account, the best possible design can only be achieved through a long iterative procedure of analysis and modification.

In this paper we introduce an integrated approach for the solution of the inverse problem: which are the lamina orientation, laminate constitution, core quality and thickness combination ensuring specified objective(s) to be reached?

The solution is obtained by integrating around an associative data base - sensitivity analysis and mathematically stringent optimization methods (MMA-Method of Moving Asymptotes) with finite element analysis, interactive graphic pre- and post-processing and parametric modelling - as implemented in OASIS-ALADDIN.

Thus the optimization of local and global geometry; laminate and lamina thicknesses; material orientation (e.g. fiber angles); and material quality (e.g. sandwich foam core densities) can be performed. The shape optimization concept is based on parametric B-rep solid modelling formulations and is fully 3-D. Objective and constraint functions may be structural weight, mass moment of inertia, stiffness, natural frequency, stresses and material cost, as well as arbitrary linear combinations of these. Objective and constraint functions may also be defined as explicit linear functions of the design variables. The objective may be given as minimizing or maximizing a single function or a combination of several functions, or as minimizing the maximum of a set of functions.

This approach has been applied to the design of adaptive blades in composite materials -i.e blades having the ability to automatically adjust their geometry and structural characteristics during operation in response to external adverse stimuli. The objective is to take advantage of the anisotropic properties of composite materials to produce a blade with a varying pitch depending on loadings. The blade must deform towards a lower angle of attack when the pressure load increases, resulting in reduced vibration, noise and cavitation.

1.1 Composite materials

Compared with conventional materials, composites offer very attractive properties at the cost of increased complexity. Composite materials are made of reinforcing fibers -in principle of continuous length- embedded in a polymeric matrix. These materials defined as plies -layer or lamina- then being laid up, under a specific sequence, form a laminate. A laminate can incorporate any number of plies themselves made of any combination and proportion of fiber and matrix, with the material coordinates of each layer oriented differently, or not, with respect of the laminate coordinates. A sandwich is a particular case of laminate in which the ply located at mid-plane is excessively thick and light in comparison to others.

The classical laminate theory shows that plies constitution, thickness and orientation, laminate lay-up and stacking sequence command the global laminate properties. The intrinsic heterogeneity of composite materials allows for each of these parameters to be modified and therefore to alter the overall laminate properties.

1.2 Inverse problem in structural design

Modern numerical techniques, such as the Finite Element Method, are today commonly used for validation of a structural design with respect of a more or less complex set of requirements. Unless the initial design fulfills the requirements, an iterative process of modification and analysis is performed until a satisfactory solution is found. This process can quickly become cumbersome when many parameters -and their interaction- must be taken into account, as it is the case with composite materials.

Using stringent optimization techniques with efficient sensitivity analysis and non-linear mathematical programming methods, it is possible to reverse and automate this procedure, by defining in a single problem the objective, the constraints and the design variables. Solving this type of problem can be defined as the solution of an inverse problem.

In mathematical terms the problem is often stated as:

$$\begin{array}{lll} \text{minimize:} & w(x) & \text{objective function} \\ \text{subject to:} & g_i(x) \geq \bar{g}_i, \quad i=1,I & \text{constraints} \\ \text{with:} & \underline{x}_j \geq x_j \geq \bar{x}_j, \quad j=1,J & \text{design variables} \end{array}$$

where $w(x)$ is the objective function to be minimized, and $x_j, j=1,J$ is the set of design variables. \underline{x}_j and \bar{x}_j are the lower and upper limits, respectively, for the design variables, $g_i(x), i=1,I$ are the constraints and \bar{g}_i their limits.

In the case of composite materials, design variables can be ply orientations, layer thicknesses, material quality, stacking sequence, which can be varied as to produce laminates with specific properties or of minimum weight, while constraints on maximum allowable stress level or minimum stiffness for instance, are satisfied.

1.3 Optimization Methodology

The optimization is a non-linear, implicit problem and can not be solved with any direct method. Instead a sequence of convex explicit sub-problems must be created which may converge to a true optimum. Each sub-problem is an approximation based on first order information of the objective function and the constraint function and their derivatives with respect to the design variables.

The procedure is iterative, each iteration involving an analysis and design phase. Starting from a design proposal, or an existing design, the automatic and iterative process of analysis and

modification will improve the design until a convergent solution, or a solution that satisfies the designer, is reached. In each iteration, an FE-analysis of the structure is performed to evaluate the properties of interest (i.e the objective and constraint functions). Then, the derivatives of these functions are evaluated with respect to the design variables. Based upon this information, the approximate subproblem is formulated and solved, and new values for the design variables are calculated -Fig. 1.

2. OASIS-ALADDIN

OASIS-ALADDIN is a specialized code for optimization of mechanical structures in the linear response domain. OASIS-ALADDIN integrates around an associative data base, interactive pre- and post- processors, a finite element solver and a parametric B-rep solid modeler. An important aspect of OASIS-ALADDIN is the modularity of the system: FE solver, solid modeler, pre- & post- processor can be replaced by other codes if preferred [1]. Specialized features for material modeling and results analysis of composite materials are available in ALADDIN. Calculation of local angles of orthotropy with respect to the geometry is automatically carried-out. Models generated in ALADDIN are completely parametric [2,3]. OASIS, the optimization engine, performs sensitivity analysis and contains several optimization algorithms and options that allow the solution of a large variety of problems, e.g continuous and discrete. It includes mathematical programming methods: linear/inverse approximation and MMA - Method of Moving Asymptotes, requiring information on the values of the objective and constraint functions as well as their derivatives with respect to design variables. In OASIS, gradient calculations are based on semi-analytical derivatives, resulting in high computational efficiency [4]. The increase in computational cost with respect to the number of design variables is only linear, allowing problems with very large number of variables, 1000 or more, to be solved without prohibitive computational cost. A detailed theoretical description of OASIS can be found in [5].

Design variables are:

- geometrical shape (control point coordinates)
- shell and membrane thicknesses (both laminate and lamina for composites)
- angles of orthotropy (e.g fiber angles)
- material quality (e.g selection of sandwich core density)
- cross section areas of rods

Design variables can be continuous or discrete, and any combination of both types can be used simultaneously, thus allowing concurrent shape and sizing optimization. Shape variables may be combined to define slave variables, and may also be used as passive design parameters.

Following factors can be used as objective and constraint functions:

- structural weight
- mass moment of inertia
- stiffness
- natural frequency
- stresses
- material cost

as well as arbitrary linear combinations of these.

Objective and constraint functions can also be formulated as explicit, linear functions of the design variables. The objective may be given as minimizing or maximizing a single function or a combination of several functions, or as minimizing the maximum of a set of functions. Several constraints may be applied simultaneously.

2.1 Optimization algorithm

MMA is a convex approximation method developed by K. Svanberg [6]. MMA is an iterative method: in each iteration a convex subproblem, which approximates the original problem, is generated and solved. An important role in the generation of these subproblems is played by a set of parameters which influence the "curvature" of the approximations, and also act as "asymptotes" for the subproblem. By moving these asymptotes between each iteration, the convergence of the overall process can be stabilized.

2.2 Finite Element Formulation

The type of element used is a general doubly curved, layered isoparametric sandwich shell element, with eight nodes and five degrees of freedom per node developed by Wennerström and Bäcklund [7, 8, 9]. The formulation is based on the same fundamental approximations suggested by Ahmad, Irons and Zienkiewicz [10, 11, 12], completed by the so-called reduced integration technique developed by Zienkiewicz [13] and by Pawsey and Clough [14, 15]. The main benefit of this improved numerical integration technique is that thin shell structures analysis can also be analyzed [16].

Upper and lower faces are assumed to be in state of plane stress: bending and shear effects are not taken into account locally in the facings. The core stiffness matrix is modified as to include transverse shear stiffness. This element is well suited for the analysis of sandwich laminates with anisotropic laminated facings. See Fig. 3 for definition of nodal locations, variables and geometrical properties.

3. DESIGN OF ADAPTIVE BLADES IN COMPOSITES

3.1 Problem formulation

Which are the laminates thicknesses, constitution and orientation as well as blade internal structural lay-out so the difference with the stipulated behaviour is minimal? Objectives being specified on deflection vs loads, and on twisting angle vs loads.

A two-phase approach was adopted in the formulation of the problem in order to reduce its complexity, as no existing design could provide a starting point. First the correct deflection was sought, then in a second phase the correct path of deformation of the blade. Thus the optimization was performed in two phases, the first concentrating on finding the optimal material distribution and structural lay-out as to obtain the specified behaviour and the second on finding the optimal laminate orientations and distribution of laminate thicknesses. For simplification purpose in this paper, the internal structure lay-out is referred to and represented as a beam. Details and specific data cannot yet be disclosed due to confidentiality requirements.

3.2 Modeling

The geometric and structural shape of the blade was described using ALADDIN. All subsequent data required by the FE-analysis and the optimization: loads, boundaries, material properties, design variables, objective functions and constraints, are associated to this CAD model. Shape design variables are connected to CAD points so they directly and automatically affect the geometry. The FE-model contained 374 8-node isoparametric layered shell elements, c.a 4500 d.o.f. - Fig. 4.

3.3 Materials and Laminates

Laminates were modelled using material properties which by themselves were design variables dependent on fiber content as well as fiber quality - Fig. 5.

3.4 Loads

All loads applied to the structure in this study were hydrodynamic pressure load distribution and were fully parametrized, as to ensure modeling coherence during the optimization procedure.

3.5 Design variables

Sizing design variables were assigned to the thickness, orientation and quality (fiber ratio, fiber type) of laminates in different part of the structure and of the beam - Fig. 6. Shape design variables were attached to the beam geometry in order to control the shape and dimension of the beam as well as its position along the chord - Fig. 7.

3.6 Constraints

Constraints were set on maximum stresses in laminates and on deformations in the shells. Stress constraints were applied to all elements in the model, specifying a maximum allowable value for Tsai-Hill failure criterion. Geometrical constraints were applied to the overall blade profile.

3.7 Results

The following results have been achieved so far:

1. The specified behaviour was effectively obtained, both in mode and amplitude - Fig. 8;
2. Deformations and stresses were kept within allowed values;
3. Initial results of prototype testing confirm design validity;
4. Starting from a symmetric profile, an asymmetric profile has been obtained.
Profile deformation control will be the object of further study.

4. CONCLUSION

Composite materials are unique in their capacity of being tailored to meet specific requirements. Structural design with composite materials naturally tends to the formulation of an inverse problem.

With the integration of modern numerical methods: FEM, sensitivity analysis and non-linear optimization with specialized parametric modeling techniques, as implemented in OASIS-ALADDIN, an efficient tool for solving inverse problems in composite structural design has been developed.

The successful design of adaptive blades in composite materials demonstrated that the problem of tailoring the laminate constitution, thickness and fibers angle as well as the internal structure lay out and geometry in order to minimize the difference with the specified path of deformation as to obtain the required characteristics could not have been solved with conventional design methods.

Another benefit consists in the possible automation of composite structures design, resulting in enhanced performances, shorten leadtime and lower cost compared with traditional engineering procedures.

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Fig. 1 - Optimization iterative procedure.

Fig. 2 - 8-nodes layered sandwich shell element.

Fig. 3 - Layered sandwich shell element with thickness variables.

Fig. 4 - FE-model of the complete blade.

Shape variable and one material and one thickness variable per layer.

Reference direction vector \hat{v} , variables linked to xx and zz .

Fig. 5 - Fiber-reinforced laminated composite material with design variables.

- t_k - ply thickness
- xx, zz - angles to \hat{v}
- s - shape
- mk - porosity (material quality)

Fig. 6 - Shell with design variables representation.

Fig. 7 - Beam with shape design variables representation.

Fig. 8 - Deflection and pitch at first and last iteration.